

Healthcare Financing Options and Health Insurance Utilization Among Medical Doctors in Lagos State, South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

Healthcare financing remains a critical determinant of access to healthcare services worldwide. In Nigeria, the burden of out-of-pocket (OOP) payments continues to dominate, while social and private health insurance schemes are striving to achieve up to 20% coverage. Although medical doctors are central to healthcare delivery, little is known about their personal utilization of health insurance schemes. The aim of this study was to assess the healthcare financing options used by medical doctors in a selected area of Lagos State, South-West Nigeria. This is a cross-sectional descriptive study which was conducted among 300 medical doctors who were selected in Mushin Local Government Area (LGA) of Lagos State using the multi-stage sampling technique. A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data on healthcare financing options and health insurance utilization from the selected respondents. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 26 and logistic regression tests were done with p -value set at 0.05. Many of the respondents were aware of existing health insurance schemes, although their utilization remained suboptimal. Out-of-pocket payment method accounted for 40.3%, followed by “discounts offered by employing hospitals” accounting for 32.3%. Others were social and private health insurance. Among the respondents who were enrolled in health insurance services, the utilization rate was 19% in the previous year. Despite high awareness levels, the utilization of health insurance among medical doctors in Mushin LGA remains limited. The reliance on alternative financing methods, particularly employer-subsidized services, underscores systemic issues affecting trust and satisfaction with formal insurance schemes. Strengthening the design and delivery of health insurance services is essential to improve uptake, even among healthcare providers themselves.

Keywords: *Healthcare Financing Options, Health Insurance Utilization, Medical Doctors, Mushin, Lagos State, South-West Nigeria, Out-of-Pocket Payments, Social Health Insurance, Private Health Insurance.*

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Introduction

Healthcare financing refers to the mobilization of funds for healthcare services, allocation of these funds to specified areas, and mechanisms used to pay for healthcare services (Eboh, 2016). It determines how resources are raised, pooled, and spent to ensure access to health services and promote equity in health systems. Health financing is an integral function of health systems that can enable progress towards universal health coverage by improving effective coverage and financial protection.

Healthcare financing involves the generation, allocation, and utilization of generated resources within a health system to ensure access to healthcare. Globally, it has become increasingly recognized as an area of critical policy relevance to achieve Universal Health Coverage (Eboh, 2016). It plays a key role in achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC), ensuring that everyone has access to essential health services without financial hardship. Health financing remains one among the six building blocks of health systems. The methods adopted by countries for healthcare financing is a critical factor in advancing universal health coverage (Jamili, 2023).

Healthcare financing covers three essential functions of revenue collection, risk pooling, and purchasing of health services. Revenue collection entails raising funds from different sources (taxes, social insurance systems, fees, grants, loans, etc.) to finance the health system (Cylus, 2022; Asante, 2020). Risk pooling involves combining and managing generated resources in such a way that individuals in a pool share collective health risks and, in so doing, protect enrolled members of the pool from payment of applicable health expenditures (Asante, 2020). Purchasing of health services is the transfer of generated funds to health service providers for health service delivery.

Health financing is central to the functioning of health systems and the attainment of health-related sustainable development goals, including universal health coverage (UHC) (Diaconu, 2021; McIntyre, 2007). A good health financing system is crucial for the effective performance of a country's health system (Madu, 2023; McIntyre, 2007). The health financing arrangements of a country determines who gets access to what health services, and the level of financial protection offered to the population (McIntyre, 2007).

The financial burden and economic cost of managing different chronic metabolic diseases have also been reported. The effects of some metabolic disorders arising from hormonal imbalance on female fertility have also been mentioned (Aliu-Ayo, 2023a; Aliu-Ayo, 2023b; Ikwuka, 2023e; Inya, 2023a; Inya, 2023b; Esan, 2025a; Esan, 2025b). Gametes which refer to the male and female reproductive cells (sperm and ova) are haploid and contain one set of chromosomes which could be either 1–22 X or 1–22 Y (Ikwuka, 2023a). Some of these chronic metabolic diseases belong to a group commonly referred to as metabolic syndrome diseases (MSDs) which are also associated with very high morbidity and mortality rates (Ikwuka, 2015; Ikwuka, 2017a; Ikwuka, 2017c; Ikwuka, 2023c; Ikwuka, 2023f; Ikwuka, 2024; Virstyuk, 2016). In addition, different studies have also reported associations between MSDs and high blood pressure, glucose and lipid metabolic disorders, asymptomatic hyperuricemia, systemic immune inflammation, and fibrogenesis – factors that may eventually lead to kidney damage (Ikwuka, 2017d; Ikwuka, 2017e; Ikwuka, 2018c; Ikwuka, 2018d; Ikwuka, 2019a; Ikwuka, 2019c; Ikwuka, 2022; Ikwuka, 2023d; Virstyuk, 2017a; Virstyuk, 2018a; Virstyuk, 2019; Virstyuk, 2021a; Virstyuk, 2021b).

Health financing systems affect the availability of services, who can access them, and whether people can afford them. Health financing describes more than just the money available for health; it includes all the

mechanisms, from raising funds to paying for health services (Botho University, 2023). The way a country finances its health care system is a crucial determinant for reaching universal health coverage (Jamili, 2023). This is so because it determines whether the health services that are available would be affordable for those that need them (Olatubi, et al., 2018). Increased financial stress can lead to increased oxidative stress. The major contributors to oxidative stress are free radicals such as superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and hydroperoxyl radicals and all are significant physiologically (Esan, et al., 2025). A non-radical which is significant physiologically is hydrogen peroxide (Ama, 2023; Baysah, 2023; Ikwuka, 2023b; Uche, 2023).

A good-functioning health financing system ensures that people can access the health services that they need without passing through financial difficulty, and that resources are utilized equitably. The government usually plays a pivotal role in financing healthcare in most countries, although the private sector may also play an important role (Botho University, 2023).

Nigeria practices a mix of six health financing methods (Uzochukwu, 2015).

1. Out-of-Pocket Payments (OOP):

Individuals pay directly for health services at the point of care.

- Statistics: More than 70% of total health expenditure in Nigeria is through OOP payments.
- This makes the Nigerian health system one of the most privately purchased globally.

2. Government Funding

The government allocates a percentage to health from general tax revenues.

- Statistics: Government health expenditure trends at 15–20% of total health expenditure.
- However, Nigeria is yet to attain the Abuja Declaration target of allocating 15% of the annual budget to health.

3. National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA):

A social health insurance scheme aimed at ensuring healthcare access for all Nigerians.

- Statistics: Coverage remains limited, with less than 20% of Nigerians enrolled, primarily civil servants and federal workers.

4. Donor Funding and Development Assistance:

Contributions from international agencies (e.g., WHO, USAID, Global Fund).

- Statistics: This accounts for 5–10% of total health expenditure, especially for vertical programs such as HIV, TB, Malaria, etc.

5. Private Health Insurance:

Voluntary schemes mostly used by formal sector employees or private individuals.

- Statistics: Less than 10% of the population uses private insurance.

6. Community-Based Health Insurance (CBHI):

Locally organized schemes for informal sector and communities.

- Statistics: Very low coverage of below 2%.

To surmount the challenges of Resource Mobilization, the Nigerian Government recently introduced a funding mechanism called Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHCPF), a component of the National Health Act of 2014, for the purpose of better investment within the health sector (Uzochukwu, 2015). This initiative was signed into the 2019 fiscal budget in 2018. BHCPF is

designed to provide free minimum basic healthcare to the indigent and most vulnerable population through accredited Primary Health Centers (PHCs) in each of the 36 states of Nigeria and the Federal Capital Territory (Fabong, 2023).

The BHCPF was established under Section 11 of the National Health Act as catalytic funding to enhance access to primary health care (Yusuf, 2022). It serves to finance a Basic Minimum Package of Health Services (BMPHS), improve the fiscal space for health, strengthen the national health system particularly at primary health care (PHC) level (Yusuf, 2022) by providing daily operations cost of PHCs, and enhance access to healthcare to the poor, thus contributing to overall national productivity (Fabong, 2023). The BHCPF is generated from (a) an annual grant from the Federal Government of Nigeria of not below one percent (1%) of the Consolidated Revenue Fund (CRF), (b) funds from international donor partners; and (c) funds from other sources, inclusive of the private sector (Ibrahim, 2023).

The BHCPF is executed via 3 gateways namely: (a) the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) gateway which makes available operational cost (Decentralized Facility Financing – DFF) and Human Resource for Health (HRH) for PHCs through the State Primary Health Care Board (SPHCB), (b) the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) gateway which insures the vulnerable Nigerians to access the BMPHS via the State Social Health Insurance Agencies (SSHIA), and (c) the National Emergency Medical Treatment (NEMT) gateway which is designed to cater for emergency ambulance services (Uzochukwu, 2018).

Funding through the NPHCDA gateway comprises program fund for Decentralized Facility Funding (35%), which is made up of funding for essential drugs, vaccines, and consumables (20%) as well as the maintenance of primary health care facilities, equipment, and transport (15%). The remaining 10% for the NPHCDA gateway is for human resource for PHC interventions consisting of 5% for midwives, and 5% for Community Health Influencers and Promoters (CHIPs) (Uzochukwu, 2018). The NPHCDA gateway ensures operational funding to strengthen the delivery of primary care services across Nigeria, prioritizing remote public PHCs, for poor households and populations in the lowest wealth bracket which is a crucial step towards attaining the sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Egbewole, 2024a; Egbewole, 2024b), and Universal Health Coverage (UHC) (Uzochukwu, 2018).

Health insurance is a system of advance financing of health expenditure via contributions, premiums, or taxes paid into a pool for all or part of health services specified by a plan or policy (Eboh, 2016). The National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) strengthened the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) (Obalum, 2012). The NHIS was a social health insurance program created by the Federal Government of Nigeria to complement sources of financing the health sector and to enhance access to healthcare for Nigerians (Akinyemi, 2021). The NHIS was established in 2005. However, it has been reviewed and now renamed as National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) in May 2022. The overriding update in the new NHIA is that it makes health insurance compulsory for all Nigerians and legal residents in Nigeria.

Health insurance is an indisputable tool for healthcare funding. Most developed countries have leveraged health insurance to subsidize healthcare for their citizens (Adebiyi, 2021). Of recent, health insurance is now being applied by poorer developing countries for obvious issues of deficiencies in healthcare service availability and funding which have been financed from public funding over the years.

Whereas healthcare financing explains the procedures and processes for paying for healthcare services in a nation, health insurance can be broadly divided into private and public insurance based on the funding source. In public insurance schemes, the funds are financed by the government from general or tailored taxes which help to improve healthcare access and promote equity (Uzochukwu, 2015; Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021). For optimal development of any economy, and considering the end goal which is to accomplish anticipated levels of health status and economic improvement, it must allocate adequate funding to health (Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021).

The current coverage of National Health Insurance Authority in Nigeria is estimated below 10% which is predominantly from federal government employees (Uzochukwu, 2015). Out of the few who are enrolled, only a little percentage utilizes the services of the NHIA for their healthcare. Available funds in public health insurance are often not sufficient and need to be supplemented by resources from private insurance. Private health funds are paid directly to the wallet managers, and they usually consist of non-profit and for-profit plans, and community health insurance schemes (Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021). When managed well, private health insurance helps improve access and equity in countries and reduces large out-of-pocket expenses for healthcare. They serve as a useful source of supplementary insurance to cover for health services for Nigerians who are not covered by publicly funded schemes (Chukwuma, 2024; Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021).

In the bid to attain universal health coverage, various countries have diverse levels of health insurance utilization (Chukwuma, 2024). In the United States of America, Private Health Insurance (PHI) is a crucial source of healthcare financing, responsible for around 35% of aggregate health expenses (Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021). Public insurance accounts for 44.9%, while OOP use trends at 13.5%. In the United Kingdom, there is a tax-based method that gives general healthcare through the country's National Health Service (NHS) which covers 86% of general health expenses, while PHI accounts for 2.9%, and OOP represents 11.1% (Motaze, 2015). In Nigeria, healthcare is financed largely through OOP, tax revenues, health insurance (social and private), subsidies, exceptions, deferrals, and sponsorship (Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021).

Various developing countries have commenced the Social Health Insurance (SHI) in adherence to the World Health Organization (WHO) call to move towards universal coverage (Tilley-Gyado, 2016). In Nigeria, the NHIS was created in 1999 by an act of legislation, and it later commenced operations in 2005 with the workers in the formal sector employed by the federal government (Motaze, 2015). As of 2020, 97% of Nigeria's population was not covered by any form of health insurance, the 3% of the population that were covered are provided for by the employee health coverage even though it was a social health insurance, participation was not made mandatory (Adebiyi, & Adeniji, 2021).

A study conducted in Nigeria has shown that over 90% of Nigerians pay OOP for their healthcare services (Ahuru, 2021). Some studies conducted on health insurance utilization in 2020 has also revealed low utilization of NHIS in Nigeria due to the use of substandard medicines, long waiting periods, discrimination, poor health services, low coverage across the country, low health-seeking behavior of Nigerians, use of other alternatives such as traditional/herbal medications and spiritual healing centers as well as the many exclusions in the NHIS benefit package (Eze, 2023).

Methodology

Study Area

Lagos State is one of the 36 states of Nigeria, and it is both the most populous state and the smallest in land area. Bounded to the south by the Bight of Benin and to the west by the international boundary with Benin Republic, Lagos State borders Ogun State to the east and north making it the only Nigerian state to border only one other state. Named after the city of Lagos, the most populous city in Africa, the Lagos State was created from the old Western Region (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2025).

Mushin Local Government Area (LGA) has a high number of medical doctors compared to other LGAs in Lagos State due to the presence of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH) which is a federal tertiary healthcare facility and a foremost training institute for medical doctors at undergraduate and postgraduate levels in Nigeria. LUTH has staff strength of 2,300 out of which 476 are medical doctors (Makinde, 2018). In addition, Mushin LGA has also one general hospital, five primary healthcare centers, as well as 63 registered private hospitals where medical doctors work. As stated by the Medical and Dental Council of Nigeria in 2022, the number of registered and licensed medical doctors in Nigeria was 24,000,

out of which 2,561 practice in Lagos State. No literature with specific number of medical doctors in private hospitals within Mushin LGA was found. However, there is a register of medical doctors in all the public hospitals within Mushin which puts the figure as follows (Roberts, 2015):

- LUTH - 476 medical doctors
- General Hospital, Mushin - 29 medical doctors
- 5 Primary Healthcare Centers - 75 medical doctors
- 63 registered private hospitals - Average of 2 medical doctors per hospital, approximately 126 medical doctors

Estimated total number of medical doctors in Mushin LGA – 706

Study Design

This study is a cross-sectional descriptive study utilizing a quantitative approach and a multi-stage sampling technique.

Study Population

The study population is medical doctors who work in public and private hospitals within Mushin LGA, Lagos State.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using the Cochran formula for cross-sectional studies:

$$n = \frac{Z^2PQ}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

n = sample size

Z = standard normal variate set at 1.96, which corresponds to a 95% confidence level

P = proportion in population extracted from the literature of a previous related study = 35% or 0.35 (Knier, 2024)

Q = 1 – P = 1 – 0.35 = 0.65

d = degree of accuracy desired (absolute precision), which is 5% or 0.05

$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.35 \times 0.65}{0.05^2} = 350$ respondents

With one out of seven non-response or attrition rate expected during sampling and data collection, the final sample size was maintained at 300.

Inclusion Criteria

- Medical doctors who work within Mushin LGA on a full-time basis.
- Medical doctors who consented to participate in the study voluntarily without any financial inducement.

Exclusion Criteria

- Medical doctors who work outside Mushin LGA.

- Medical doctors who did not consent to participate in the study voluntarily.

Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was utilized. In Stage 1, a stratified random sampling technique was used to select respondents from each health center by proportionate allocation. The sampling frame was drawn from Lagos University Teaching Hospital, Mushin General Hospital, 5 PHCs and 63 Private Hospitals with a total of 706 medical doctors in Mushin LGA. The hospitals, percentage contributed to the sampling frame, and assigned sample size are as follows:

Table 1. Sample Size Distribution

S/No.	Health center	No. of medical doctors	Sample size allocated
1	Lagos University Teaching Hospital	476	204
2	Mushin General Hospital	29	12
3	Papa Ajao PHC	17	7
4	Alafia/Adeoyo PHC	13	5
5	Igbehinadun PHC	14	5
6	Odusele Ola PHC	16	7
7	Odoeran/Ogunlana PHC	15	6
8	63 Private Hospitals	126	54
	Total	706	300

In Stage 2, a simple random sampling by balloting was used to select the respondents based on the sample size allocated to the health center. The medical doctors were given numbers, and the numbers were randomly selected per facility to determine the respondents.

Study Instruments

Reliability and Validity of Study Instruments

The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated tools (Capaday, 2025). The questionnaire was pre-tested on 10% of the sample size, which is 30 medical doctors in Ikeja, Lagos State. The pre-test identified that there was a deficiency in the healthcare financing options of medical doctors, and this was the discount offered by employing hospitals which was later included in the final questionnaire.

Data Collection

A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. All questionnaires were given a unique identification number that was recorded on the questionnaire. Data collected was thoroughly checked and validated for accuracy and completeness.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Simple frequency was used in describing categorical variables, while the mean and median were used to describe normal and skewed data, respectively. Chi-square and logistic regression (where appropriate) were used to test for association between independent and dependent variables with p -value set at 0.05.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital. The respondents were not influenced in any way into participating in the study. Their participation was voluntary and without consequences for non-participants. Written consent was obtained from respondents before commencement of the study. The confidentiality of the respondents was assured and maintained as unique numbers were used in assigning questionnaires, and

not names. The respondents were also assured that data obtained from them would be used solely for research purposes. The nature and purpose of the study were explained to the prospective respondents.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Female	94	31.3
Male	206	68.7
Age		
45 and above	59	19.7
35-44	111	37.0
25-34	130	43.3
Marital status		
Divorced	4	1.3
Married	153	51.0
Separated	5	1.7
Single	137	45.7
Widowed	1	0.3
Type of marriage		
Monogamous	140	46.7
Polygamous	13	4.3
Household size		
1-2	62	20.7
3-4	87	29.0
5 and above	125	41.7
Ethnicity		
Hausa	17	5.7
Igbo	106	35.3
Others	53	17.7
Yoruba	124	41.3
Religion		
Christianity	225	75.0
Islam	64	2.3
Others	8	2.7
Traditional	3	1.0
Monthly income		
Below N200,000	20	6.7
N201,000-N300,000	93	31.0
N301,000-N400,000	70	23.3
N401,000-N500,000	61	20.3
Above N500,000	56	18.7

Table 2 shows that males account for 68.7% of the respondents. It also shows that 51.0% of the respondents are married. 41.3% of the respondents are Yorubas, 75.0% are Christians, and 31.0% earned between N201,000 and N300,000 per month.

Table 3. Work-Related Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Work setting		
General Hospital	67	22.3
Primary Health Center	55	18.3
Private Hospital	106	35.3
Teaching Hospital	53	17.7
Others	19	6.3
Cadre		
Associate Professor	7	2.3
Consultant	49	16.3
House Officer	3	1.0
Medical Officer	95	31.7
Professor	10	3.3
Junior Resident Doctor	36	12.0
Senior Medical Officer	65	21.7
Senior Resident Doctor	35	11.7
Duration of practice in years since graduation		
0-3	54	18.0
4-6	72	24.0
7-9	53	17.7
10-12	69	23.0
>12	52	17.3

Table 3 shows that 35.3% of the respondents work in a private hospital, and that 31.7% are medical officers. 24.0% of the respondents have been in practice for 4 to 6 years since graduation.

Table 4. Healthcare Financing Options Used by the Respondents

Variable	Frequency (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Discount offered by employing hospital	97	32.3
HMO	22	7.3
NHIS	15	5.0
Out-of-pocket (OOP)	121	40.3
Others	3	1.0
HMO, Discount offered by employing hospital	2	0.7
HMO, NHIS	1	0.3
Medical savings, Discount offered by employing hospital	2	0.7
NHIS, Discount offered by employing hospital	7	2.3
OOP, Discount offered by employing hospital	12	4.0

Table 4 shows that majority (40.3%) of the medical doctors use out-of-pocket payment mechanism to access healthcare while 32.3% of the medical doctors use discounts offered by employing hospitals to access healthcare. 4.0% of the medical doctors use a combination of out-of-pocket and discount offered by employing hospital.

Table 5. Association between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Enrolment in Any Health Insurance among the Respondents

Variable	Enrolled in any health insurance		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Gender				
Female	24 (25.5)	70 (74.5)	5.261	0.024
Male	30 (14.6)	176 (85.4)		
Age				

25-34	37 (28.5)	93 (71.5)	19.686	0.001^f
35-44	15 (13.5)	96 (86.5)		
45 and above	2 (3.4)	57 (96.6)		
Marital status				
Ever married	25 (46.42)	138 (87)	1.920	0.542 ^f
Single	29 (53.7)	108 (78.8)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	23 (16.4)	117 (83.6)	0.686	0.487 ^f
Polygamous	1 (7.7)	12 (92.3)		
Household size				
1-2	15 (12)	110 (88.0)	2.087	0.340
3-4	15 (17.2)	72 (82.8)		
5 and above	12 (19.4)	50 (80.6)		
Ethnicity				
Hausa	3 (17.6)	14 (82.4)	2.606	0.428 ^f
Igbo	20 (18.9)	86 (81.1)		
Others	13 (24.5)	40 (75.5)		
Yoruba	18 (14.5)	106 (85.5)		
Religion				
Christianity	48 (21.3)	177 (78.7)	7.334	0.023^f
Islam	6 (9.4)	58 (90.6)		
Traditional/Others	0 (0.0)	11 (100.0)		
Monthly income				
Below N200,000	8 (40.0)	12 (60.0)	15.857	0.003^f
N201,000-N300,000	22 (23.7)	71 (76.3)		
N301,000-N400,000	14 (20.0)	56 (91.8)		
N401,000-N500,000	5 (8.2)	56 (91.8)		
Above N500,000	5 (8.9)	51 (91.1)		

Table 5 shows the association between socio-demographic characteristics and enrolment in any health insurance among the respondents. There was a statistically significant association between gender, age, religion, monthly income and enrolment in any health insurance among the respondents ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6. Association between Work-Related Characteristics and Enrolment in Any Health Insurance among the Respondents

Variable	Enrolled in any health insurance		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Work setting				
General Hospital	3 (4.5)	64 (95.5)	21.075	0.001^f
Others	7 (36.8)	12 (63.2)		
Primary Health Center	7 (12.7)	48 (87.3)		
Private Hospital	20 (18.9)	86 (81.1)		
Teaching Hospital	17 (32.1)	36 (67.9)		
Cadre				
HO/MO/SMO	36 (22.1)	127 (77.9)	12.996	0.005^f
Junior/Senior Resident Doctor	16 (22.5)	55 (77.5)		
Consultant	2 (4.1)	47 (95.9)		
Associate Professor/Professor	0 (0.0)	17 (100.0)		
Duration of practice in years since graduation				
0-3	9 (16.7)	45 (83.3)	27.700	0.001^f
4-6	25 (34.7)	47 (65.3)		
7-9	13 (24.5)	40 (75.5)		
10-12	5 (7.2)	64 (92.8)		
>12	2 (3.8)	50 (96.2)		
Employment type				
Private sector	28 (22.8)	95 (77.2)	3.206	0.051
Public sector	26 (14.7)	151 (85.3)		

Table 6 shows the association between work-related characteristics and enrolment in any health insurance among the respondents. There was a statistically significant association between work setting, cadre, duration of practice in years since graduation, and enrolment in any health insurance among the respondents ($p < 0.05$).

Table 7. Association between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Health Insurance Utilization in the Past One Year among the Respondents

Variable	Health insurance utilization in the past one year		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Gender				
Female	54 (80.6)	13 (19.4)	0.145	0.729
Male	134 (78.0)	37 (21.6)		
Age				
25-34	65 (73.0)	24 (27.0)	3.041	0.226
35-44	76 (82.6)	16 (17.4)		
45 and above	47 (82.5)	10 (17.5)		
Marital status				
Ever married	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	2.515	0.266 ^f
Married	93 (76.2)	29 (23.8)		
Single	89 (83.2)	18 (16.8)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	84 (76.4)	26 (23.6)	0.011	0.535 ^f
Polygamous	9 (75.0)	3 (25.0)		
Household size				
1-2	91 (85.8)	15 (14.2)	5.750	0.058
3-4	49 (71.0)	20 (29.0)		
5 and above	39 (78.0)	11 (22.0)		
Ethnicity				
Hausa	9 (69.2)	4 (30.8)	4.869	0.164 ^f
Igbo	72 (85.0)	12 (15.0)		
Others	31 (81.6)	7 (18.4)		
Yoruba	76 (73.8)	27 (26.2)		
Religion				
Christianity	129 (75.9)	41 (24.1)	4.851	0.095 ^f
Islam	48 (84.2)	9 (15.8)		
Traditional/Others	11 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		

Table 7 shows the association between socio-demographic characteristics and health insurance utilization in the past one year among the respondents. There was no statistically significant association between socio-demographic characteristics and health insurance utilization in the past one year among the respondents ($p > 0.05$).

Table 8. Association between Work-Related Characteristics and Health Insurance Utilization in the Past One Year among the Respondents

Variable	Health insurance utilization in the past one year		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Work setting				
General Hospital	47 (74.6)	16 (25.4)	20.881	0.001 ^f
Others	3 (37.5)	5 (62.5)		
Primary Health Center	38 (79.2)	10 (20.8)		
Private Hospital	77 (91.7)	7 (8.3)		

Teaching Hospital	23 (65.7)	12 (34.3)		
Monthly income				
Below N200,000	9 (90.0)	1 (10.0)	2.111	0.762 ^f
N201,000-N300,000	51 (76.1)	16 (23.9)		
N301,000-N400,000	43 (76.8)	13 (23.2)		
N401,000-N500,000	47 (83.9)	9 (16.1)		
Above N500,000	38 (77.6)	11 (22.4)		
Cadre				
Associate Professor/Professor	12 (70.6)	5 (29.4)	7.434	0.059
Consultant	41 (89.1)	5 (10.9)		
HO/MO/SMO	98 (81.0)	23 (19.0)		
Junior/Senior Resident Doctor	37 (68.5)	17 (31.5)		
Duration of practice in years since graduation				
0-3	34 (79.1)	9 (20.9)	4.673	0.354 ^f
4-6	29 (67.4)	14 (32.6)		
7-9	31 (79.5)	8 (20.5)		
10-12	53 (82.8)	11 (17.2)		
>12	41 (83.7)	8 (16.3)		
Employment type				
Private sector	80 (89.9)	9 (10.1)	10.171	0.002 ^f
Public sector	108 (72.5)	41 (27.5)		

Table 8 shows the association between work-related characteristics and health insurance utilization in the past one year among the respondents. There was a statistically significant association between work setting, employment type, and health insurance utilization in the past one year among the respondents ($p < 0.05$).

Table 9. Association between Work-Related Characteristics and Ever Enrolled in Any Health Insurance among the Respondents

Variable	Ever enrolled in any health insurance		χ^2	p-value
	No (%)	Yes (%)		
Work setting				
General Hospital	4 (6.0)	63 (94.0)	31.568	0.001 ^f
Primary Health Center	7 (12.7)	48 (87.3)		
Private Hospital	22 (20.8)	84 (79.2)		
Teaching Hospital	17 (32.1)	36 (67.9)		
Others	11 (57.9)	8 (42.1)		
Monthly income				
Below N200,000	9 (45.0)	11 (55.0)	18.522	0.001 ^f
N201,000-N300,000	26 (28.0)	67 (72.0)		
N301,000-N400,000	14 (20.0)	56 (80.0)		
N401,000-N500,000	5 (8.2)	56 (91.8)		
Above N500,000	7 (12.5)	49 (87.5)		
Cadre				
Associate Professor/Professor	0 (0.0)	17 (100.0)	13.357	0.004
Consultant	3 (6.1)	46 (93.9)		
HO/MO/SMO	41 (25.2)	122 (74.8)		
Junior/Senior Resident Doctor	17 (23.9)	54 (76.1)		
Duration of practice in years since graduation				
0-3	10 (18.5)	44 (81.5)	33.105	0.001 ^f
10-12	5 (7.2)	64 (92.8)		
4-6	29 (40.3)	43 (59.7)		
7-9	14 (26.4)	39 (73.6)		
>12	3 (5.8)	49 (94.2)		

Employment type				
Private sector	34 (27.6)	89 (72.4)	6.875	0.013
Public sector	27 (15.3)	150 (84.7)		

Table 9 shows the association between work-related characteristics and ever enrolled in any health insurance among the respondents. There was a statistically significant association between work setting, monthly income, cadre, duration of practice in years since graduation, employment type, and ever enrolled in any health insurance among the respondents ($p < 0.05$).

79.0% of the respondents have never been enrolled in any health insurance, and 62.7% of the enrolled respondents have not utilized health insurance in the past one year.

Table 10. Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-Demographic Characteristics, Work-Related Characteristics, and Ever enrolled in Any Health Insurance

Variable	Coefficient	AOR	95%	CI	p-value
Gender					
Female					
Male	.532	.160	1.702	.810	3.574
Age					
25-34		.282			
35-44	.655	.215	1.924	.684	5.417
45 and above	1.845	.176	6.328	.437	91.715
Religion					
Christianity (Reference)					
Islam	.851	.117	2.342	.809	6.781
Work setting					
Primary Health Center		.007			
General Hospital	1.406	.077	4.081	.860	19.365
Private Hospital	-.280	.595	.756	.269	2.123
Teaching Hospital	-1.152	.085	.316	.085	1.173
Others	-1.117	.118	.327	.081	1.325
Monthly income					
Below N200,000		.179			
N201,000-N300,000	.996	.111	2.708	.795	9.225
N301,000-N400,000	1.258	.072	3.520	.893	13.879
N401,000-N500,000	1.361	.119	3.901	.705	21.601
Above N500,000	-.309	.775	.734	.088	6.148
Cadre					
HO/MO/SMO		.437			
Junior/Senior Resident Drs	-.143	.793	.866	.297	2.526
Consult/ Assoc. Prof./Prof.	1.704	.236	5.498	.328	92.074
Duration of practice in years since graduation					
0-3		.063			
4-6	-1.326	.013	.266	.093	.758
7-9	-1.530	.020	.217	.060	.788
10-12	-.580	.530	.560	.091	3.430
>12	-.543	.758	.581	.018	18.291

Table 10 shows logistic regression analysis of socio-demographic characteristics, work-related characteristics, and ever enrolled in any health insurance. There is no statistically significant association between socio-demographic characteristics, work-related characteristics, and ever enrolled in any health insurance, meaning that being enrolled in any health insurance is not dependent on socio-demographic characteristics, nor work-related characteristics.

Table 11. Logistic Regression Analysis of Socio-Demographic Characteristics, Work-Related Characteristics, and Health Insurance Utilization

Variable	Coefficient	AOR	95% CI	CI	p-value
Religion					
Christianity (Reference)					
Islam	-.628	.139	.533	.232	1.228
Work setting					
Primary Health Center		.127			
General Hospital	.258	.581	1.294	.519	3.228
Private Hospital	-.163	.888	.849	.088	8.167
Teaching Hospital	.581	.254	1.788	.659	4.849
Others	1.978	.033	7.228	1.173	44.523
Employment type					
Private sector					
Public sector	.936	.380	2.550	.315	20.610

Table 11 shows the logistic regression analysis of socio-demographic characteristics, work-related characteristics, and health insurance utilization. There is no statistically significant association between socio-demographic characteristics, work-related characteristics, and health insurance utilization implying that health insurance utilization is not dependent on socio-demographic characteristics, nor work-related characteristics.

Healthcare Financing Options

In this current study, the identified healthcare financing options utilized by medical doctors in Mushin Local Government Area include out-of-pocket payments which represent 40.3%, discount offered by the employing hospital which represents 32.3%, Health Maintenance Organizations (HMOs) which represent 7.3%, National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) which represents 5.0%, and others.

This current study highlights the availability of a certain healthcare financing option which is poorly represented in most of the available literature. This healthcare financing option is called discount offered by employing facilities. It is attributable to the fact that medical doctors are capable of treating themselves for primary illnesses, as such do not require hospital visits or consultations for primary care, and this could justify why some employing hospitals provide this offer in the employment package of medical doctors. This is understood to be a work incentive geared towards providing access to healthcare at no cost within the work environment. With the availability of this option, health insurance utilization would be expected to decrease among medical doctors. This option must have accounted for the poor health insurance utilization among the respondents. However, this disagrees with a study conducted recently in South-east Nigeria (Pillah, 2023) which revealed that majority of the medical doctors use out-of-pocket payment mechanism for their healthcare bills. This is in line with poor health insurance coverage of about 4% reported in Nigeria, and which has a negative effect in attaining universal health coverage. NHIS is a social insurance scheme and is expected to help reduce out of pocket spending (Adebisi, & Adeniji, 2021).

Nonetheless, a study in South-south Nigeria found that insured civil servants have comparable average healthcare and total healthcare costs per visit compared with the non-insured civil servants (Egonu, & Ilo, 2023). Non-insured federal civil servants were found to spend catastrophically for health services as much as their insured counterparts, though health insurance is supposed to reduce catastrophic health expenditure for households (Adebisi, 2021; Egonu, & Ilo, 2023). Unlike another study in South-east Nigeria which identified health insurance as the second most widely utilized healthcare financing option among the study participants (Pillah, 2023), this current study identified discount offered by the employing facility as the second most widely used healthcare financing option.

Health Insurance Utilization

The rate of health insurance utilization in this current study is 12.3% while the rate of National Health Insurance Scheme utilization is 5.0%. This is consistent with a study conducted in South-east Nigeria where the rate of National Health Insurance Scheme utilization was found to be less than 5.0% (Pillah, 2023). The finding also reflects the rate captured in the National Health Insurance Authority which puts the coverage of health insurance below 10.0% (Alawode, 2021). In this current study, health insurance utilization is low and signifies the need for more enrolment among medical doctors in Mushin Local Government Area of Lagos State.

On the other hand, metabolic syndrome diseases (MSDs) are interrelated diseases that contribute significantly to healthcare costs, morbidity, and mortality rates, thus requiring the search for new, effective, and innovative treatment options (Ikwuka, 2024). Innovative treatment options such as combining HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, SGLT-2 inhibitors, and angiotensin II receptor blockers (type 1) i.e. A2RB (AT1), have shown clinical effectiveness indicated by marked improvements in the metabolic functions of the heart, liver, pancreas, and kidney (Ikwuka, 2017b; Ikwuka, 2018a; Ikwuka, 2018b; Ikwuka, 2021; Virstyuk, 2017b; Virstyuk, 2018b; Virstyuk, 2018c; Ikwuka, 2024). Additionally, Glucagon-like Peptide 1 Receptor Agonists (GLP-1 RAs) such as liraglutide have been shown to improve the clinical outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension (Ikwuka, 2019b).

Prospects for further studies include identifying and understanding the various factors responsible for low health insurance utilization even among people with high health insurance enrolment.

Conclusion

This study unraveled a well-utilized healthcare financing option among medical doctors in Mushin Local Government Area of Lagos State which is discounts offered by employing hospitals. Health insurance in Nigeria is unarguably an indispensable strategy for ameliorating the poor health indices of the country and reducing out-of-pocket expenditure for quality healthcare services. Enrolment in health insurance schemes was high among medical doctors employed in the public sector because it is compulsory for them. However, this health insurance utilization was observed to be very poor despite the compulsory enrolment. Many of the medical doctors employed in the private sector have poor health insurance enrolment and utilization indices.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors guarantee responsibility for everything published in this manuscript, as well as the absence of a conflict of interest, and the absence of their financial interest in performing this research and writing this manuscript.

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